

GENDER DIFFERENCE IN COGNITIVE EMOTION REGULATION OF ANGER ACROSS DEVELOPMENTAL STAGES

ABSTRACT

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Purpose of the present paper is to investigate gender difference at three developmental stages: adolescence, adulthood and elder-hood. For this purpose a sample of 120 subjects was derived from the general population of rural areas of district Saharanpur, U.P. Each group of adolescents, adults and elders has 40 subjects which consist of equal number of male and females to make a 2x3 experimental design with two dependent variables: cognitive emotion regulation and emotion of anger. To have as representative sample as possible, stratified random sampling was conducted. Data collection was done with inventories of 'Cognitive Emotion Regulation Questionnaire' and 'Negative Emotions Scale'. Result showed that there is a significant difference between adolescents and adults with respect to 'emotion of anger' and cognitive emotion regulation. And this difference remains consistent between male and female at the stage of adolescence. But, except this, no significant gender difference was found at the stage of adulthood and elder-hood with respect to both dependent variables.

Keywords: Cognitive Emotion Regulation, Emotion of Anger, Adolescence, Adulthood, Elder-hood.